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Making a tutorial for water sampling and selection of transects

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Abstract	This document describes how a tutorial for sampling in a citizen science project can be made.
Keywords	Pesticides - Insecticides - Dragonflies - Sampling - Citizen Science

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Insecticides and dragonflies

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1. Introduction

This document describes the design of a method for environmental sampling in a citizen science project. We describe the choices made for a pilot project and the reasoning behind them. This illustrates factors that need to be considered and can be used when designing a sampling scheme. Within the pilot we select suitable transects from the Dutch Dragonfly Monitoring Scheme to study the impact of pesticides on dragonflies and how samples should be taken and treated. This is a part of the ACTION-pilot “insecticides and dragonflies”. The goal of this pilot is to gain insight into the impact of pesticides on dragonfly communities. However many citizen science projects have citizens collecting samples and potentially run into similar issues. This document describes the reasoning behind the decisions we made and aims to give insights to those running citizen science projects on how to engage with an established cohort of citizen scientists to gather additional samples or data.

Dutch Butterfly Conservation (<https://www.vlinderstichting.nl/english>) is a non-profit organisation that studies butterflies, dragonflies and moths in order to advise management organisations and better protect these species. One of the core activities is the monitoring of these groups, this is primarily done with citizen scientists that count animals according to a standardized protocol. To understand why certain species or groups of species are doing poorly, additional research is done. This research can be independent of the monitoring, even if it is inspired by the monitoring results, or incorporated in the monitoring. In the latter case we can use the wealth of data the monitoring program provides. In the current proposal we will do that latter and measure pesticides on locations where dragonflies are being monitored (<https://www.vlinderstichting.nl/wat-wij-doen/meetnetten/meetnet-libellen/>). This is a citizen science pilot study of the H2020-SwafS-2018-1-824603 EU project. More info about the project at <https://actionproject.eu/>

We quite often see that citizen science projects already have a community of citizens that in one way or other are involved. This asks for a specific approach. An existing relation makes some things easier. However, you do not want to burden citizen scientists with too many additional tasks. This means that you have to be careful not to ask additional questions too often and, keep them linked to the core activity. Additionally you want to set up a sampling campaign that is easy, clear but also will give you a result that answers your questions in the end. This document describes how we made these decisions and generalise this as a guide for other citizen science projects.

At the end of this document the communication we send to the citizen scientists is attached.

2. Insecticides and dragonflies

Insecticides and other pesticides are widespread in the environment. These compounds are all tested in laboratories but their impact under natural conditions are poorly known. In typical conditions multiple compounds can be found at the same time and may interact and the environment is far from those in laboratory studies. In the recent study by Barmiento et al. (2019) we found that, under natural conditions, damselfly larvae were negatively affected by low concentrations of the neonicotinoid thiacloprid.

Since 1999 Dutch Butterfly Conservation has run a monitoring program for dragonflies where dragonflies are counted along transects by citizen scientists following a protocol. This is done on more than 500 transects a year and allows us to calculate trends in the abundance of dragonflies in the Netherlands. We would like to build on this data to research whether there is a correlation between pesticide presence in water and dragonfly prevalence. Our transects are in nature reserves but also in parks and agricultural areas. This allows us to select locations that differ in their exposure to pesticides. Samples of water will be collected from these sites by the same citizen scientists who count the dragonflies. Testing of the samples for pesticides requires sophisticated laboratory equipment, and is carried out by students at the University of Applied Sciences in Leiden.

The citizen scientists in this project are interested in dragonflies and often have a personal connection with the location where they count dragonflies, often for years already. Participants mention this regularly in personal contact and has been confirmed in an motivation analysis done within ACTION. It is therefore likely that gaining knowledge on the presence of pesticides on their location is of interest. An important drive of people involved in this project is to contribute to our understanding of trends in dragonflies. Insight in the role of pesticides in the occurrence of dragonflies is therefore a logical addition. Already in early stages we communicate that both these aspects will be analysed and given as feedback. The response of volunteers was very positive and many indicated that they want to participate in this additional analysis.

For other citizen science projects the details will be different but keeping additional questions close to the core of the main project and connect it to the drive of the citizens is always important. The questions should be of interest to the citizen scientist too, and

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connect to his or hers location/conditions. The essence is that the communication should emphasize solving a question together, not the citizen scientist helping someone. This can only be done convincingly when it addresses something the citizens are inherently interested in.

*Barmantlo, S. H., Vriend, L. M., van Grunsven, R. H. A., & Vijver, M. G. (2019). Environmental levels of neonicotinoids reduce prey consumption, mobility and emergence of the damselfly *Ischnura elegans*. Journal of Applied Ecology, 56(8), 2034-2044.*

Figure 1. Blue tailed damselfly is declining in the Netherlands and exposure to pesticides is a possible cause of this decline (Photo: Kim Huskens).

3. Selection of samples

Often the number of samples that can be taken or processed is limited. In our case that is the number of transect that can be sampled. What constitutes a sample differs between studies but in most cases there are individual measurements. There are some key aspects that have to be considered when deciding which cases or transects should be sampled. In this way it will be practical, the data can actually be used and we avoid biases. The selection of samples is naturally dependent on citizen scientists that indicate that they want to contribute. There are some criteria that make samples more or less suitable.

Sample design should be based on the statistical analysis that will be done. Very important is whether the factor is continuous or categorical. In the first case a regression analysis is more appropriate, testing for a (linear) relation between factors, in the second case an ANOVA makes more sense. An theoretical example is if you want to study the effect of agricultural management on vitamin levels of apples. If you want to study the role of fertilizers or organic versus conventional farming. In the first case you can sample a range of fertilizer levels, not just low and high but also intermediate and do a regression analysis. In the second case an apple is either from an organic or conventional farm, a regression is not possible and an ANOVA approach is more appropriate. Fairly often only samples at high and low levels are taken for continuous factors. In that case a regression is not appropriate but an ANOVA approach reduces the power substantially, this should be avoided. In our case, pesticide concentrations are a continuous variable and thus should be sampled over the entire range.

So the main factors to consider designing the sampling are:

- There should be enough background data on the samples. Amplies should have sufficient data to make comparisons possible. In our case the trassects should at least be counted regularly over the last years. Transects that just started or have only been counted infrequently may give a less accurate estimate of the local dragonfly populations. Which factors are relevant differs from project to project but needs to be made explicit.
- The sampling should reflect the factor studied. In our case we want to investigate the impact of pesticides on the dragonfly fauna. This is a continuous factor, there are concentrations of pesticide, not mere presence or absence. This means that this variation should be present in the samples.

4. Sampling procedure

The actual sampling by the Citizen Scientists should be relatively low effort and straightforward. In our case it is done when they are in the field to count dragonflies. Therefore there is no additional travel time involved. We will supply suitable containers, 150 ml tubes with screw caps, and ask the volunteers to sample the same location when they count dragonflies. This way it is very simple and as we supply the containers standardised. Recording the information to identify samples is essential. Often this can be quite simple. They should record the location, preferably take a photo, hold the container under water, a few centimeters below the surface in this way the sampled water will be representative and not just surface water. On each container the following things should be noted with waterproof marker after the sample is closed:

- Date
- Transect name
- Transect number
- Section number
- Name of the person taking the sample

A photo of the sample location should be provided when possible. This is always helpful when interpreting results, a photo can give a lot of information and nearly everyone has a phone with a camera. Noting the name and number of the transect may seem redundant but this is on purpose. This is essential information and this way we can always check whether it is correct. Sometimes local names are used but mistakes in numbers are possible as well. Photos nowadays often have coordinates as well, that give the sampling location. It is however risky to rely on these as it happens quite often that a photo is taken before the GPS has an accurate fix.

The container should be kept out of the sun and stored cool, in the freezer or fridge. The samples will be collected for analysis and brought to the lab. In the lab all samples will be numbered and the other information stored in a spreadsheet with the number of the sample. The step from the field to the lab (or central place where the data will be analysed) is a good moment to check whether everything is complete and record all samples.

Communication with the citizen scientists is well organised as they already participate in the monitoring scheme. We therefore regularly send them newsletters and many will be present at the annual meeting of the Dutch Butterfly Conservation where this project will

be presented as well. Citizen scientists that are interested will be sent a Dutch instruction with the sample containers (attached).

Naturally samples should only be taken where and when the water can be reached without risk for the person taking the sample. When designing a sampling scheme, the potential risks to the citizen scientists need to be considered and avoided, these can be exposure to toxic chemicals or dangerous situations. For this particular pilot, we expect at least some water bodies to contain pesticides, this will however be strongly diluted and the concentration far below a level where it would be any risk to the citizen scientist. The risks involved are therefore negligible. If you are to undertake a similar project then consider undertaking a similar risk assessment.

Figure 2. An example of a dragonfly monitoring transect with four sections. All dragonfly species are counted for each section.

5. Chemical Analysis

The identification and measurement of complex organic compounds, such as pesticides, is highly specialised and requires techniques such as gas chromatography

(GC) and high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC). This is not feasible with citizen scientists. We identified possible partners that are able to do these analyses through our network and contacted a research group that uses these techniques and teaches students how to develop protocols for specific questions. The analysis of the samples will now be done at the University for Applied Sciences Leiden under the supervision of Dr. Peter Lindenburg. Several protocols for similar questions have been developed here in the past. Students will optimize the necessary techniques in collaboration with DBC and with advice from Prof. Martina Vijver, an expert on pesticide exposure in aquatic ecosystems. Dr. Peter Lindenburg is a biologist and biopharmaceutical scientist and has specialised in the measurement of low concentrations and quantities of organic compounds and currently works at Analytical BioSciences and Metabolomics at Leiden University and Metabolomics at the University for Applied Sciences Leiden. He will be the primary supervisor for the analysis, he and his team have a wealth of experience in the measurement of low concentrations of complex compounds through HPLC and GC. As the number of people involved is much smaller than with the sampling everything can easily be discussed in this case. To prevent different expectations we did start this well before sampling and the sampling regime is adjusted to fit the requirements of the analysis, e.g. the volume per sample has increased to increase sensitivity. If there is an external partner doing part of the analysis it is very helpful to discuss what they need and what they will deliver in detail.

6. Statistical Analysis

The concentrations of pesticides will likely not be independent from each other, as it is expected that certain pesticides frequently co-occur, and therefore we will apply a correspondence analysis. We will correlate the main axes of this analysis with the monitoring data on the dragonflies. This will give us insight into whether the occurrence of dragonflies, in both number, trend and species richness, is related to the exposure to pesticides. For this analysis we need to have a continuous distribution of pesticide levels as described in the sampling procedure.

7. Feedback to the citizen scientists

It is essential that the citizen scientists involved will get feedback. For long term project that is obvious as people are still involved. For short term projects it is sometimes overlooked. The results from this study will be communicated to the citizen scientists through the newsletter of the monitoring scheme. This will be a generalized story over

the relationship between pesticides and dragonflies The individual citizen scientists will also get the concentrations measured at their transects with an indication whether those levels are high or low.

8. Main points

When developing a citizen science activity as described above, with citizens that are already involved but an additional activity is planned there are some main things to consider:

- Make sure you do not ask too much from the citizen scientists. This means not doing additional things too often and keep it easy with little additional effort.
- Only address questions that match the interest of the citizen scientists, therefore it is important to understand their motivation.
- Invite citizen scientists to take on this additional task but make it very clearly optional.
- Think about the background data needed for your analysis and make sure this exists for the cases where you collect the additional data.
- Already think about the expected distribution of your data and the statistical analysis needed for this type of data when designing the sampling scheme.
- Be clear in your communication and include what citizen scientists can expect as feedback.
- Give feedback both for the overall results but also for the individual citizen scientists as they are often interested in their local situation.

Supplement 1: Section in the newsletter to all citizen scientists monitoring dragonflies

Bestrijdingsmiddelen

Dankzij jullie tellingen hebben we een goed beeld van hoe het met de libellen gaat in Nederland. Met die informatie kunnen we libellen ook beschermen. Verbetering van de waterkwaliteit en goed beheer zijn daarbij van groot belang. Soms zijn de oorzaken van voor- of achteruitgang eenvoudig te zien, maar dat is niet altijd het geval.

De laatste jaren blijkt dat libellen erg gevoelig zijn voor bestrijdingsmiddelen. Ook als de middelen niet direct in het water worden gebruikt, komen ze daar vroeger of later wel in terecht. Daar hebben ze effect op de dieren die in het water leven. Dit zou weleens kunnen verklaren waarom er in veel agrarische gebieden zo weinig libellen leven. Maar dit is niet eenvoudig te zien aan het water. Daarom willen we dit nu samen met Hogeschool Leiden en het EU-project ACTION gaan onderzoeken en daar hebben we jullie hulp bij nodig.

Door watermonsters van een aantal routes te analyseren en de gegevens te vergelijken met de libellengegevens kunnen we inzicht krijgen welke stoffen een effect hebben. Hiervoor hebben we naast de telgegevens ook watermonsters nodig om te analyseren. Daarom willen we vragen wie hieraan mee wil werken.

Bij het lopen van de route zullen een aantal monsters genomen moeten worden (4 buisjes van 50 ml) die daarna koud bewaard moeten worden. Dit kan elke twee weken gedaan worden bij het tellen van de route. Na de zomer halen we deze op en worden ze in het laboratorium gemeten.

Tel je een algemene libellenroute en lijkt het je interessant hieraan mee te werken, stuur dan een email naar roy.vangrunsven@vlinderstichting.nl met een korte beschrijving van het type water waar je telt en waar dat in Nederland is. Om een goede verdeling over verschillende watertypes te hebben zullen we een selectie maken van de routes. Helaas is het niet mogelijk om voor alle routes een analyse te doen.

Supplement 2: Email inviting citizen scientists:

Beste teller,

Zoals laatst in de nieuwsbrief gemeld willen we dit jaar naar bestrijdingsmiddelen kijken. We weten dat deze een effect op libellen (en andere insecten) kunnen hebben maar weten niet hoe dat in de praktijk zit. Daarom willen we graag weten welke pesticiden er bij libellenroutes in het water zitten. Hiervoor hebben we jullie hulp nodig.

Als je hieraan mee wil werken zorg ik dat je monsterbuisjes krijgt per post. Deze kunnen dan bij het tellen van de libellen gevuld worden met water (3 keer 50 ml) en koel bewaard worden. Aan het eind van het seizoen zorg ik dat ze weer opgehaald worden. Daarna gaan de monsters naar het laboratorium van de Hogeschool Leiden waar ze doorgemeten worden. Je krijgt dan te horen wat er in je monsters gevonden is en er zal een vergelijking over alle bemonsterde routes gemaakt worden.

Ben je benieuwd wat er in het water zit waar je telt? Wil je weten of er op plekken met meer bestrijdingsmiddelen minder libellen vliegen? Nu kunnen we dat bepalen.

Als je mee wil werken kun je mij een email sturen, ik zorg dat je monsterbuisjes ontvangt en een korte uitleg. Het bemonsteren zou niet meer dan een paar minuten moeten kosten bij het tellen.

Met vriendelijke groeten,

Roy van Grunsven

en de rest van het meetnet team.

Supplement 3 : Dutch Instructions send with sample containers

Mennonietenweg 10
Postbus 506
6700 AM Wageningen
T 0317 46 73 46
info@vlinderstichting.nl
www.vlinderstichting.nl
IBAN NL70INGB0005134425
IBAN NL63TRIO0212488074
BTW-nr. NL009193431801
KvK 41048624

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Geachte Libellenteller,

We zijn erg blij dat zoveel mensen positief gereageerd hebben op onze vraag of ze watermonsters willen nemen om bestrijdingsmiddelen te kunnen meten. In deze envelop zitten buizen die geschikt zijn om monsters mee te nemen. Omdat de concentraties aan bestrijdingsmiddelen laag zijn hebben we per monster vrij veel water nodig, 150 ml dus drie buizen. Met 6 buizen kan dan twee keer een monster genomen worden op dezelfde plek.

Dit is vrij eenvoudig:

- Bij het tellen van een (algemene) libellenroute moet een plek gekozen worden waar je goed bij het water kunt. Als je niet overal de kleine soorten telt, dan graag een monster nemen in een sectie waar alles geteld wordt.
- Open een buis en houdt hem enkele centimeters onder het wateroppervlak zodat hij vol loopt (als je hem te ondiep houdt, krijg je veel spul dat op het water drijft).
- Sluit de buis goed en schrijf er het routenummer, sectie, de datum en je naam op met watervaste stift.
- Maak indien mogelijk een foto van de plek waar het watermonster genomen is.
- Neem de drie volle buizen mee en bewaar deze koel, in de koelkast of vriezer.

Door bij twee tellingen een monster te nemen op dezelfde plek krijgen we een beter beeld dan bij een eenmalige meting. Het is daarom van belang dat er minstens een week tussen de twee monsters zit maar ze op dezelfde plek genomen zijn. Na het libellenseizoen gaan de buizen naar de hogeschool in Leiden waar in het laboratorium door studenten de bestrijdingsmiddelen gemeten gaan worden. Uiteraard krijg je de resultaten van deze metingen voor jouw locatie en gaan we kijken of we patronen zien over alle locaties samen en daarmee of we kunnen zien dat die bestrijdingsmiddelen een effect hebben op de libellen.

Sommige tellers tellen meerdere routes, dat is natuurlijk heel fijn maar we kunnen niet overal meten en willen de metingen graag spreiden. Welke route je wil bemonsteren is aan jou. Indien routes door meerdere personen geteld worden dan graag onderling afspreken wie waar bemonsterd.

Met vriendelijke groeten,
DE VLINDERSTICHTING

Roy van Grunsven

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